

Reinstatement and lectotypification of *Ixora lanceolaria* Colebr. (Rubiaceae) –a little known endemic species from the Western Ghats, India

E.S. Santhosh Kumar^{1,*}, S. Shailajakumari¹, Divya N. Murali¹, P. Suresh Kumar¹, V.S. Deepa Lekshmi²

¹Jawaharlal Nehru Tropical Botanic garden and Research Institute, Palode, Karimankode P.O., Thiruvananthapuram district, Kerala-695562, India.

²Department of Botany, Iqbal College, Peringamala, Peringamala P.O., Thiruvananthapuram district, Kerala-695562, India.

*Corresponding author. Email: santhoshkumares@gmail.com

Abstract

Ixora lanceolaria Colebr., an endemic species of the Western Ghats, often treated as a synonym of *I. malabarica* (Dennstedt) Mabberley is reinstated as a distinct species and a lectotype for this name is designated here.

Introduction

Ixora Linnaeus is the third largest genus of the family Rubiaceae, comprising of about 530 species (Mouly et al., 2009; Davis et al., 2009), distributed in tropical and subtropical regions of the world. In India, the genus is represented by 46 species (Hooker, 1880; Bremekamp, 1937, 1938, 1959; Husain & Paul, 1989, 1991; Sivadasan & Mohanan, 1991; Deb & Rout, 1992; Pradeep, 1997), of these, the Western Ghats represented by 19 species of which 10 are endemic to the region. The genus can be recognized from its allied genera by the articulated petioles, narrowly tubular tetramerous flowers, bilobed stigmas, bi-locular ovaries and fruits (or rarely with more than two locules), uni-ovulate locules and seeds with a large adaxial hilar cavity (De Block, 2007). The centre of species diversity for the genus is South-East Asia, in particular Borneo (Lorence et al., 2007).

Ixora malabarica (Figure 1) was described based on Rheede's *Kilckola-tsjetti* mentioned in Hortus Malabaricus (10:113.t.57.1690). It was August Wilhelm Dennstedt, who first determined Rheede's plant as *Chiococca malabarica* in 1818. Later, it was variously interpreted as *Ixora leucantha* Wallich ex G.Don, *I. lanceolaria* Colebr., *I. barbata* Roxburgh ex Smith, etc., and finally Mabberley (1977) opined that Rheede's plant belongs to *I. malabarica*. It is a vulnerable species endemic to the Western Ghats (IUCN, 2001).

Accepted: 13 December 2018
Published: 17 December 2018

© 2018 Kumar et al.

Distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Disclaimer:

I3 Press discourages plagiarism, falsification and exaggeration of contents. We welcome valid and constructive criticisms/complaints on our published articles, which will be published on upcoming issues without any processing charge or APC.

Figure 1. *Ixora malabarica*.

A. Habit, B. A twig, C. Fruits, D. Type of *Ixora malabarica* (reproduced from Rheede's *Hortus Malabaricus*, 10:113.t.57.1690).

Henry Thomas Colebrooke, a British colonial magistrate and an ardent Sanskrit scholar, was proposed the name *Ixora lanceolaria* in an unpublished manuscript (?), but was validated by William Roxburgh with a proper description in 1820 (see [Roxburgh, 1820](#)). The original collection was from a native plant introduced by Andrew Berry in his garden in Calcutta from Travancore in 1808. Andrew Berry was an English biologist and one among the twelve member botanist group of Bengal called 'The United Brothers' working on its plants under the instigation of John Gerard Koenig. Since its original publication, only [Hooker W.J. \(1848\)](#), [Hooker \(1880\)](#) and [Gamble \(1921\)](#) have been considered it as a distinct species and rest of all other workers from India and elsewhere considered it as a synonym of *I. malabarica* or *I. leucantha* ([Mabberley, 1977](#); [Husain & Paul, 1989](#); [Govaerts, 2003](#); [Barbhuiya & Dutta, 2013](#); [Nicolson et al., 1988](#); [Nayar et al., 2006, 2014](#)).

During the systematic study on the genus *Ixora* in Kerala, the authors observed that several collections of this taxon was erroneously identified either as *I. malabarica* or *I. gamblei* V.S. Ramach. & V.J. Nair [= *I. leucantha* var. *malabarica* Gamble] ([Ramachandran & Nair, 1988](#)). On critical study with type and related specimens, description in the protologue and examination of fresh field collections reveals that this species is very distinct from the morphologically closely allied species such as *I. malabarica* or *I. gamblei*. Therefore, it is reinstated and treated here as a distinct species along with detailed description, photographs and other pertinent notes for its easy identification.

Taxonomy

Ixora lanceolaria Colebr. in Roxb., Fl. Ind.1:397.1820; DC., Prodr.4:488.1830; Wight & Arn., Prodr. 1:428.1834; Wight, Icon.t.827.1844; Hooker,W.J., Curt. Bot. Mag. 74 (3): t.4399. 1848; Hook.f., Fl. Brit. India 3:138.1880; Rama Rao, Fl. Pl. Travancore 212.1914; Gamble, Fl. Pres. Madras 630.1921. *I. colebrookii* Voigt, Hort. Suburb. Calcutt. 391.1845. *I. wallichii* Wight ex Hook.f. (illegitimate), Fl. Brit. India 3: 138. 1880. Type:—INDIA, Wallich Cat. No. 6125 (right hand specimen) (K-00112323!; lectotype, designated here)

Description

Erect shrubs, 1–3 m high; young branches spreading, very slender, grey, pubescent, later glabrescent; internodes 2–8 cm long. Leaves petiolate; petiole 5–10 mm long, channeled above; blade linear-lanceolate, 6–18 × 1.5–4 cm, rounded or very shortly acute at base, gradually acuminate at apex, entire along margin, glabrous on both sides, dark green above, pale beneath, opaque, sub-coriaceous; lateral nerves many, more or less perpendicular to the mid rib, forming sub-marginal arches. Stipules

Figure 2. *Ixora lanceolaria*.

A. A twig, B. Stipule, C. Bract, D. Calyx showing bracteoles, E. L.S. of calyx and ovary, F. A flower, G. A stamen, H. A fruit.

triangular with a subulate tip, 0.5–0.7 cm long, glabrous or slightly hairy when young. Inflorescence cymose, terminal, pendulous, peduncle 2–5 cm long, pubescent, with a pair of reduced leaves at the base, 3–7 × 1–2.5 cm, cordate at base, gradually acuminate at apex; bracts linear, 5–7 mm long, pubescent; bracteoles 3–4 mm long, sparsely pubescent. Flowers sessile or shortly pedicellate; pedicels to 1–3 mm long, hairy; calyx tube ca. 1–1.5 mm long, glabrous, lobes 4, 3–4 mm long, glabrous or slightly hairy along the margins, green; corolla greenish white, tube 1.5–2.5 cm long, glabrous; lobes oblong, 8–10 × 2–2.5 mm, obtuse at apex. Stamens 4, attached at mouth of corolla; filaments to 3.5 mm long, glabrous; anthers linear, 6–8 mm long, apiculate at apex, sagitate at base. Ovary 2-celled; ovule one in each locule; style slender, as long as corolla tube, 1.8–2.3 cm long, tip fusiform, longitudinally cleft forming two stigmatic lobes; lobes 2–3 mm long, exceeding corolla tube. Fruit globose, red, smooth, crowned with 4 subulate erect calyx teeth. Seed hemispherical.

Flowering and fruiting:—December–July.

Additional Specimen examined:—INDIA, Robert Wight 484 (E-image!); Robert Wight 1340 (BR-image!); Kerala: Thiruvananthapuram district, TBGRI Garden site, 25 January 1985, N. Mohanan 905 (TBGT!); *ibid.*, 02 September 2003, Mathew Dan 47737 (TBGT!); *ibid.*, Glasmin Syrus 71206 (TBGT!); Adipparambu, M. Abdul Jabbar & E.S. Santhosh Kumar 14780 (TBGT!). Kollam district, Cherukara, 29 January 2004, Deepthi & Geetha 53120 (TBGT!).

Distribution:—India (Assam, Cachar); Myanmar (Rangoon, Thingungyun).

Lectotypification of *Ixora lanceolaria*

Within the protologue of *Ixora lanceolaria*, William Roxburgh mentioned that the plant was introduced into Kolkata Botanic Garden in 1808, that it flowered in hot months and fruited in the rainy season. He did not cite any specimen for his species in the protologue. Roxburgh died in 1815 and he might have seen the specimens in 1808 and wrote the description before 1814. Wallich Catalogue no. 6125 came in 1831–32, and this number should not be connected with a type specimen seen by Roxburgh before 1814 and there is nothing available at Central National Herbarium (CAL), where majority of Roxburgh's collections available. Most of the later workers cited Wallich Catalogue no 6125 as the type for this taxon and there are two specimens mounted on this sheet. It seems that the plant mounted on the left bearing the number 6125 and there is another specimen on the right side of the same sheet without any number found suitable for a lectotype designation (K.N. Gandhi-Pers. Comm.). Hence it is selected as the lectotype here (Figure 2, 3).

Note:—*Ixora lanceolaria* is similar to *I. malabarica* and *I. gamblei* but can easily be distinguished by the linear-lanceolate leaves with broadest

Figure 3. *Ixora lanceolaria*.

A. Lectotype of *I. lanceolaria* (right hand specimen), **B.** A twig, **C.** Habit, **D.** Colour drawing from Curtis Botanical Magazine (Volume 74(3):t.4399.1848), **E.** Illustration from Robert Wight's *Icones Plantarum Indiae Orientalis* (t.824.1844).

region near the base, greenish yellow sweet scented flowers in lax corymbs, corolla lobes distinctly shorter than the tubes.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to the Director, JNTBGRI for the facilities provided. They are also thankful to the Board of Trustees, Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew for permitting us to use the photograph of the type specimen and to Mr Anurag N Sharma for the photographs of *Ixora malabarica*.

References

- Barbhuiya, H.A. & Dutta, B.K. (2013) A new distributional occurrence of *Ixora malabarica* (Rubiaceae) from Assam India. *Phytotaxonomy*. 13, 155-156. [as *Ixora malabarica*]
- Bremekamp, C.E.B. (1937) The *Ixora* species of Burma and Andaman Islands. *J. Bot.* 75,108–111, 169–175, 260–266, 295–293, 318–326.
- Bremekamp, C.E.B. (1938) The *Ixora* species of Burma and Andaman Islands. – Additions and Emendations. *J. Bot.* 76, 330–336.
- Bremekamp, C. E. B. (1959) New *Ixora* species from Bengal, Burma and the Nicobar Islands. *Indian Forester*. 85, 371–375.
- Davis, A.P., Govaerts, R., Bridson, D.M., Ruhsam, M., Moat, J. & Brummitt, N.A. (2009) Global assessment of distribution, diversity, endemism, and taxonomic effort in the Rubiaceae. *Annals of the Missouri Botanical Garden*. 96, 68–78. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3417/2006205>.
- De Block, P. (2007) Three new Madagascan *Ixora* species (Rubiaceae) with flowers up to 23 cm long. *Nordic Journal of Botany*. 25, 75–84.
- Deb, D.B. & Rout, R.C. (1992) Two New Species of *Ixora* (Rubiaceae subfam. Ixoroideae) from India and Burma. *Kew Bull.* 47, 295–300.
- Gamble, J.S. (1921) *Ixora* in *Flora of the Presidency of Madras*. Vol. 2. London, Adlard & Co. pp. 627–632.
- Govaerts, R. (2003) *World Checklist of Selected Plant Families* Database in ACCESS: 1-216203. The Board of Trustees of the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew.
- Hooker, J. D. (1880) *Ixora* L. In: *Flora of British India* 3:137–149. London, L. Reeve & Co.
- Hooker, W.J. (1848) *Ixora lanceolaria* -Lance leaved *Ixora*. *Curtis's Botanical Magazine*, Vol. 74, ser. 3. London, Bentham Reeve and Reeve.
- Husain T. & Paul, S.R. (1989) *Taxonomic studies on the genus Ixora L. (Rubiaceae)*. *Journal of Economic and Taxonomic Botany Additional Series* 6. Jodhpur, India, Scientific Publishers.

- Husain, T. & Paul, S.R. (1991) *Ixora manantoddii*, a new species of *Ixora* L. (Rubiaceae-Pavetteae) from India. *Bulletin du Jardin Botanique National de Belgique*. 61, 15–19.
- Nayar, T. S., Rasiya, B., Mohanan, N. & Kumar, G.R. (2006) *Flowering Plants of Kerala - A Handbook*. Thiruvananthapuram, Tropical Botanic Garden and Research Institute.
- Nayar, T.S., Rasiya, B. & Sibi, M. (2014) *Flowering Plants of the Western Ghats, India*, Vol. 2. Palode, Jawaharlal Nehru Tropical Botanic Garden and Research Institute.
- Nicolson, Dan, H., Suresh, C. R. & Manilal, K. S. (1988) *An interpretation of Van Rheedee's Hortus Malabaricus*. Königstein, Koeltz Scientific Books. p.199.
- IUCN (2001) *IUCN Red List categories. Version 3.1. Prepared by the IUCN Species Survival Commission*. IUCN, Gland, Switzerland and Cambridge, UK. Available from:
<https://portals.iucn.org/library/sites/library/files/documents/RL-2001-001.pdf>.
- Lorence, D.H., Wagner, W.L., Mouly, A. & Florence, J. (2007) Revision of *Ixora* (Rubiaceae) in the Marquesas Islands (French Polynesia). *Botanical Journal of the Linnaean Society*. 155, 581–597.
- Mabberley, D.J. (1977) Francis Hamilton's Commentaries with Particular Reference to Meliaceae. *Taxon*. 26 (56), 523-540.
- Mouly, A.S., Razafimandimbison, G., Khodabandeh, A. & Bremer, B. (2009) Phylogeny and Classification of the species-rich Pantropical showy genus *Ixora* (Rubiaceae-Ixoreae) with indications of geographical monophyletic units and hybrids. *American Journal of Botany*. 96, 686–706.
- Pradeep, A.K. (1997) A new species of Rubiaceae from India. *Nordic Journal of Botany*. 17, 315–317.
- Ramachandran, V.S. & Nair, V.J. (1988) *Flora of Cannanore*. Kolkata, Botanical Survey of India. p.599.
- Roxburgh, W. (1820) *Flora Indica or Descriptions of Indian Plants*. Vol. 1. Serampore, The Mission Press. p. 493.
- Sivadasan, M. & Mohanan N. (1991) *Ixora agasthyamalayana*, a new species of Rubiaceae from India. *Botanical Bulletin of Academia Sinica*. 32, 313–316.